

Fig. S1

Yoshiicerus persimilis
Tomocerus vulgaris
Tomocerus qinae
Tomocerus nigrus
Tomocerus maximus
Pogonognathellus longicornis
Pogonognathellus flavescens
Plutomurus gul
Novacerus tasmanicus
Harlomillsia oculata
Oncopodura yosiana
Cyphoderus albinus
Salina celebensis
Lepidocyrtus fimetarius
Sinella curviseta
Dicranocentrus wangi
Orchesella cincta
Paranurophorus simplex
Desoria trispinata
Folsomia candida
Pseudobourletiella spinata
Ceratophysella communis

Fig. S2

(a)

(b)

(c)

(e)

(f)

(a)

(b)

(c)

(e)

(f)

(a)

(b)

(c)

(e)

(f)